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A STUDY OF SOME FACTORS INFLUENCING PROGRESSIOM AND PERFORMANCE OUTCOMES OF OVERSEAS STUDENTS AT A UK UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

The ever increasing diversity of the student population within the higher education sector presents challenges for educators. Universities need to adapt in order to provide inclusive learning environments that meet these students' varying educational needs, as well as to develop appropriate support mechanisms. In particular, a fundamental requirement is the development of a better understanding of the needs of international students, who are often learning in a second language, in addition to experiencing unique cultural, social, and financial challenges. An improved understanding can potentially assist in developing guidelines and best practice for supporting these groups of students.

This study looks at whether perceptions of lower progress and outcomes for international students progressing into year 2 of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering undergraduate degrees at Queen's University Belfast, from a diploma programme, are valid. Their performance is tracked from their diploma year, through to graduation. In order to isolate areas of concern particular to the international student group, results are compared with a control group of UK students also progressing into year 2 from a Foundation Degree programme. We also report on qualitative surveys carried out to identify areas that the students perceive to be problematic. It was found that while the international students experienced minor practical difficulties, they actually performed better than the comparison group. It appeared that difficulties were more related to joining the programme at year 2 rather than year 1, and the expected transition issues unique to international students may have already been addressed during their diploma year.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Increasing Internationalisation in Higher Education

The past decade has shown a steady increase in the number of international students choosing to study in the UK. Data from the Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA) shows that overall numbers of international students increased by 11% in the five year period from 2014 to 2018. A particularly significant increase has been seen in the Northern Ireland region, which would have traditionally had low numbers of international students. In the same 5-year period Queen's University Belfast (QUB) saw a 46% increase in the number of international students. Within the School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering (SMAE) at QUB, this trend was also seen with a 59% increase in international student numbers between 2015 and 2018. These trends are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Trends in international student numbers from 2014 to 2018 (a) QUB and UK Totals (data source: HESA) and (b) School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering at QUB (UG and PG)

1.2 Challenges of Internationalisation

The performance of international students, in particular those who are studying in a second language, can fall below expectations for certain groups. Varying factors, including different countries of origin (and thus previous educational background), differing cultural norms, and English language proficiency, can result in poorer outcomes. For example a study by Li et al [1] showed a correlation between poorer performance of Chinese students compared to other international students due to English language ability and more difficulties with social integration in UK universities, while Rienties et al [2] found good social and academic integration of international students from Western countries, but lower academic and social integration from non-Western students.

In terms of the relative effect of these factors, English language proficiency is an obvious challenge, particularly for Engineering students who are faced with the additional challenges of technical English [3–5]. A study by Mulligan et al showed numerous difficulties faced by students from non-English speaking backgrounds, with a majority reporting significant difficulty understanding lecture, taking notes, and gaining deeper understanding [6].

1.3 Rationale for the Study

The School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering at Queen's University Belfast has a current undergraduate enrolment of 730 students, 110 of whom are international students. Within the school, there has been a general perception that international students have poorer outcomes than local students in undergraduate degree programmes. In order to assess the validity of this perception and address any potential underlying issues, initial steps were taken to better analyse the data that is available for these students and determine if there are any trends that can be identified. This paper presents the initial work that was carried out, with the three aims as follows:

- To track the performance of a group of international students from entry to an undergraduate degree in the School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering through to completion;
- To track a comparable control group of local students;
- To aim to identify any unique areas of difficulty for the groups.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Selected Groups

Entry into undergraduate programmes in the United Kingdom generally occurs after the completion of the equivalent of A level study, and students progress into year 1 of their degree programme. As there are limited numbers of international students entering the SMAE programmes via this "standard" route, two other groups of students were selected for comparison, both of whom join the programme at year 2, after a period of study elsewhere.

(a) INTO students (International Students)

Queen's University partners with a pathway provider, INTO University Partnerships, and the largest number of international undergraduate students in SMAE come via this route. The vast majority of these students are from Asian and Middle Eastern countries, and most students progressing into engineering degrees come from a one year diploma programme. This programme offers the students the opportunity to study at the equivalent of year one, but in much smaller classes. Students also attend English language classes in addition to their subject modules. On successful completion of the programme, students may progress directly into year 2 of the university undergraduate programme. Progression requirements are that the students obtain a minimum of a 60% module average, with passes in all 10 engineering modules, in addition to achieving the required English Language standard (equivalent to IELTS 6.0).

(b) Foundation degree students (UK nationals)

It was felt that comparing the INTO students directly to UK national students entering by a conventional route into year 1 was problematic, for two reasons:

1. The minimum required academic qualifications for entry to the INTO Year 1 Diploma programme is lower than for students directly entering Year 1 of their undergraduate degree through the conventional route.
2. The effect of joining a degree programme at year 1 vs year 2 may be significant.

It was therefore decided to select a group of UK students who progressed to the University via a Foundation Degree (FD) at Belfast Metropolitan College (BMC), a local further education college. These students are more comparable as the minimum entry requirements are similar to the INTO programme, and the students also join the main degree programme at year 2. Requirements for progression are a 55% module average, with passes in all elements of all modules.

2.2 Analysis of Performance

An analysis of the data available for both sets of students was carried out. The numbers of students commencing on the Foundation Degree or INTO Diploma programme were tracked through to the numbers progressing into SMAE. The performance of both sets of students admitted between 2010 and 2018 across the stages was analysed, and the final degree classifications compared.

2.3 Student survey

Students from the two groups were surveyed in order to assess their perceptions and views in a number of areas including practical and social issues, transition issues moving from foundation study to the main university, and academic issues. Surveys were sent to all relevant students active in SMAE degree programmes in June 2019 from the two entry routes. For comparison purposes, a group of INTO students who were at the end of their year at INTO were asked the same questions about their experience at INTO, in order to assess any bias in perceptions due to the passage of time. A 5 point likert scale was used, and responses were collated and weighted to give an average score out of 10 for each question. For some issues, such as those relating to language, questions were omitted from the FD student survey.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Performance and Outcomes

Table 1 shows the completion data from students who first joined the FD programme, or the INTO Diploma programme between the years 2010-2015. It can be seen that the percentage of INTO students who were eligible to progress into SMAE from the programme was higher, at 80%, than the eligible percentage from the foundation degree 72%, and the actual percentage who chose to continue into year 2 was 75% compared with 61% respectively. In addition to this, the percentage graduating, and graduating with either a 1st class or 2:1 degree classification is also notably higher for the INTO cohorts.

Table 1. Performance of UK Foundation Degree Students and the INTO International students

	Foundation Degree		INTO Diploma	
	Number	% of enrolled students	Number	% of enrolled students
Students enrolled on initial programme	140		99	
Students eligible to progress into year 2 SMAE	101	72%	79	80%
Students actually progressing into year 2 SMAE	85	61%	74	75%
	Number	% of stage 2 entrants	Number	% of stage 2 entrants
Graduated students	67	79%	60	81%
Students obtaining 1 st class degree	4	5%	7	9%
Students obtaining 2:1 degree	16	19%	17	23%
Students obtaining 2:2 degree	35	41%	23	31%
Students obtaining 3 rd class degree	10	12%	10	14%
Students obtaining BSc ordinary degree	2	2%	3	4%
Students withdrawn/Failed/Not completed	18	21%	14	19%

3.2 Survey Results

Results were collated from the surveys. Responses were obtained from 12 students who were just finishing their year at INTO (35% response rate), and 19 ex-INTO students who had subsequently transitioned into QUB (28% response rate). There was a more limited response was obtained to the foundation degree student survey, with only 7 responses (20% response rate).

3.2.1 Practical Issues

The results from questions around practical issues such as orientation, registration, and accommodation issues are presented in Table 2. Among INTO students and FD students, satisfaction levels with practical issues were generally high at both stages. Ex-INTO students looking back on their time at INTO had slightly higher perceptions of the ease of issues compared with current INTO students, but the differences were not very significant. For FD students financial issues were the most difficult, and this continued at both stages.

Table 2. Ratings for question “How easy were the following practical issues”

	INTO Students surveyed at end of INTO year	INTO students surveyed during time at QUB about their time at INTO	INTO students surveyed during time at QUB about their time at QUB	Foundation degree students surveyed during time at QUB about their time in foundation degree	Foundation degree students surveyed during time at QUB about their time in QUB
Organising transport, visas, travel documents	7.5	7.50	7.37		
Completing registration forms	7.17	8.24	7.5	8.57	8.57
Organising accommodation	7.5	7.79	7.19	6.88	8.33
Orientation (finding your way around, knowing where things are)	7.69	7.94	8	7.86	8.21
Adjusting to the climate	6.43	7.34	8		
Managing finances	7.32	8.13	8.03	6.07	6.07
Making friends	7.68	7.79	7.03	8.57	6.43
Coping with the language	7.88	8.01	7.5		
Homesickness, missing family and friends	7.12	7.33	7.66	8.33	8.33
Cooking, cleaning, shopping	8.33	7.94	8.09	8.5	9.28
Average	7.46	7.80	7.64	7.83	7.98

The INTO students initially found the most difficult issue “adjusting to the climate”, with many originating from countries with much warmer and drier weather than Northern Ireland, although this improved significantly by the time the students transitioned into year 2 at university. Issues with homesickness, finances and orientation showed modest improvements between the INTO year and year 2, in line with reasonable expectations as the students become more accustomed to living abroad. At odds with this however, is the small decrease in how the INTO students coped with the language, as this would also be expected to increase after a year spent in an English speaking environment.

The largest decrease for the INTO students was in the ease with which they felt they could make friends, again this is not unexpected due to transitioning to a much bigger class size, integrating culturally with local students, and also perhaps due to entering the programme at year 2, when social groups would already have been established among students who entered the university at year 1. What is particularly striking, and more unexpected, is that this difficulty in establishing friend groups is even more pronounced among the local students transitioning into stage 2, which would seem to indicate that the transition at year 2 itself is more problematic than language or cultural issues from a social perspective. Comments from both the INTO students and the local students on this issue were very similar when asked what was difficult about the learning environment, and what advice they would give to others, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Selection of comments illustrating difficulties in social integration

INTO Student Comments	<p><i>“Having no friends in class just those who came from INTO”</i></p> <p><i>“A lot of the students already have formed their own friend group when you enter during stage 2, so it’s a bit difficult to make friends with existing students. I found myself making friends with new entry students like myself.”</i></p>
Foundation Student Comments	<p><i>“Students joining QUB from BMC may find it harder to make friends with students who started QUB at stage 1, however interact with them and try talk to other students - having friends who are doing the same course is really useful for help with exams and assignments etc.”</i></p> <p><i>“The academic transition is fine. It’s the social element that can be hard but if you have made friends [during Foundation Degree] and they’re in your position you can stick together. Eventually you make friends from the QUB class but takes time”</i></p>

3.2.2 Course Content

The results relating to the students' experiences of the course content, and their preparedness for study at each level are presented in Table 4. In all areas, other than the expectations of course content and difficulty levels, the INTO students were less confident with their ability to cope with the course content at university compared to their INTO year.

Both INTO students and local students felt less confident with their Mathematical knowledge when transitioning to university than they had done previously. They also both showed a drop in their interest levels on transitioning to year 2. On the first point this may just be attributable to a natural increase in the level of difficulty, or may be due to the fact that students entering directly to year 1 of the degree programme are required to have at least a B grade in A level Mathematics. The second point may be due to normal academic fatigue, or recognised problems around motivation on transition to university [7,8]. It would be interesting to compare both areas in direct entry students transitioning from year 1 to year 2.

Table 4. Ratings for question "What was your experience of the course and module content?"

	INTO Students surveyed at end of INTO year about INTO	INTO students surveyed during time at QUB about their time at INTO	INTO students surveyed during time at QUB about their time at QUB	Foundation degree students surveyed during time at QUB about their time in foundation degree	Foundation degree students surveyed during time at QUB about their time in QUB
The classes were at the right level of difficulty	6	5.94	6.05		
You were prepared for the level of study	7.5	7.34	6.45	7.14	7.5
You were interested in the subjects	8.04	7.50	7.11	8.21	7.5
Your existing knowledge of Mathematics was sufficient to allow you to understand	7.83	8.28	6.84	8.93	7.86
Your existing level of English was sufficient to allow you to understand	8.17	7.97	7.24		
The course content was as you expected	7	7.34	6.58	7.86	8.21
Average	7.51	7.41	6.74	7.68	7.68

3.2.3 Teaching

Table 5 shows the satisfaction levels of the students relating to teaching at both their pre-university year and at university. The results for both INTO students and the FD students were remarkably similar, with INTO students showing an average satisfaction in this area of 7.65 while at INTO, 8.42 for those looking back at their INTO experience, and 6.77 while at QUB, and FD showing satisfaction of 7.85 looking back at their foundation degree, dropping to 6.19 at QUB.

Table 5. Ratings for question “What was your experience of teaching?”

	INTO Students surveyed at end of INTO year about INTO	INTO students surveyed during time at QUB <u>about their time at INTO</u>	INTO students surveyed during time at QUB <u>about their time at QUB</u>	Foundation degree students surveyed during time at QUB <u>about their time in foundation degree</u>	Foundation degree students surveyed during time at QUB <u>about their time in QUB</u>
Spoke at the correct pace	7.86	7.81	6.97		
Used language that you could understand	8	8.13	6.97	8.21	7.5
Were prepared to help you individually	7.33	8.28	6.45	8.14	5.71
Made the content clear and easy to understand	7.5	8.44	6.71	7.5	6.07
Responded to feedback from the class	7	8.91	6.71		
Gave you appropriate feedback	7.5	8.91	6.84	7.86	6.07
Provided you with the information you needed	7.83	8.75	6.71	8.21	7.14
Used helpful resources	8	8.44	7.11		
Encouraged you to participate	7.83	8.13	6.45	7.14	5.71
Average	7.65	8.42	6.77	7.85	6.19

It would appear that these differences in experience are mainly due to the transition from small group teaching to very large class sizes, and the more anonymous environment of the university, as illustrated by comments in Table 6.

Table 6. Selection of comments illustrating difficulties in transition to large lecture teaching

INTO Student Comments	<p><i>“Very big lecture theatre. No individual attention. Difficult to ask questions”</i></p> <p><i>“could easily approach professors in INTO for help but wasn't that easy to approach the professors at University that easily”</i></p>
Foundation Student Comments	<p><i>“Because of the lack of contact and communication between students and lecturers, the learning</i></p> <p><i>“Less caring than the [Foundation degree] lecturers”</i></p>

4 SUMMARY

Tracking the performance of two specific populations of international students and UK students, both entering undergraduate degrees in Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering at year 2, shows that a higher percentage of the international students successfully complete their initial period of study and achieve their progression requirements than the UK students.

Both UK and international students struggled socially when they moved into year 2 in the university, and showed significant drops in the ease of forming friendship groups. On other practical issues, the international students coped well overall, finding the greatest difficulty in adjusting to the colder climate initially. Most practical issues became easier over time, with the exception of a small increase in difficulty coping with the language, presumably due to moving to a large lecture based programme. UK students on the other hand found most difficulty in managing their finances, and this persisted as an issue before and after their transition.

In terms of academic content, the international students experienced a drop in confidence levels and in feelings of preparedness in most areas when transitioning into university. The local students displayed only a drop in their

confidence with mathematics. Both groups showed lower interest levels after transitioning to stage 2. Both groups of students showed clear preference for the small group teaching that they had experienced in their foundation programmes, and drops in satisfaction levels were found across all areas for both groups on transitioning to university.

Final outcomes for the students showed a slightly higher percentage of international students completing the degree, compared to the UK students, and a notably higher percentage of international students achieving first class or 2:1 degree classifications. This suggests potentially higher levels of motivation or resilience in the international cohort.

The practical implications of this study suggest that more work needs to be done to assist the transition of students who are entering degree programmes at a different stage to the main student body, regardless of the origin of the students.

Further work will be carried out to assess the performance of international students entering at year 1 compared to UK students entering at year 1 once the population size is sufficient. The effect of having a transition year in small classes in assisting international students to settle into a new country should be assessed, as many of the expected difficulties for international students seem to already have been resolved during the diploma year for this cohort. A study of the effect of different nationalities and native languages will also be considered.

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